

Innovative Ex-situ Biological Biogas Upgrading Using Immobilized Biomethanation Bioreactors Combined With Micro Sorbents

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Abstract

Biogas upgrading enhances energy value by increasing methane content. This study investigates an ex-situ biological upgrading approach using immobilized biomethanation bioreactors (IBBRs) with micro sorbents. Microporous organic polymers (MOPs: XDV1, XDV3) and powdered activated carbon (PAC) were incorporated into hydrophilic polyurethane (HPU) matrices to improve H₂ and CO₂ adsorption, enhancing hydrogenotrophic methanogenesis. Semi-batch and continuous lab-scale IBBRs were tested to assess the impact of gas recirculation and micro sorbents on methane production, H₂ consumption, and CO₂ removal. XDV1 exhibited the highest CH₄ enhancement due to superior gas adsorption capacity. Reducing recirculation lowered methane yield, but MOPs-alginate reactors achieved the highest CH₄ (83%), surpassing PAC-based systems. Hydrogen consumption was highest in MOPs-alginate reactors, confirming enhanced gas transfer efficiency. These results highlight micro sorbents as an effective tool for optimizing biomethanation, offering a scalable solution for biogas valorization.

Keywords (maximum 6 in alphabetical order)

Biogas Upgrading, Hydrogenotrophic Methanogenesis, Micro Sorbents, Methane Production

INTRODUCTION

Biogas, produced through anaerobic digestion (AD) of organic waste, consists of 60–70% methane and 30–40% CO₂, with trace gases like H₂S, H₂, and water vapor. While useful for heating and power, its high CO₂ content lowers energy value, increases transport costs, and limits feasibility. Upgrading biogas to ≥90% methane enhances its applications and economic potential [1].

Conventional upgrading methods rely on physical (pressure-based, membrane, cryogenic) or chemical (scrubbing) techniques to remove CO₂ with minimal CH₄ loss. This study explores a biological approach, using methanogenic microorganisms as self-replicating catalysts to convert CO₂ together with H₂ into CH₄ via hydrogenotrophic methanogenesis [2]. An up flow immobilized biomethanation bioreactors (IBBR) were used previously by our group for ex-situ biogas upgrading [3]. The granular methanogenic microorganisms were immobilized using a composite hydrophilic polyurethane (HPU) foam polymeric-based matrix, which was shown to secure the biomass from sudden inhibitory shock loads as well as prevents biomass washout from anaerobic digestion-AD reactors [4] [5].

Still, hydrogen is considered a poorly soluble gas, its bioavailability and consumption by hydrogenotrophic methanogens is challenging. One of the ways for increasing hydrogen consumption rate is by increasing the mixing inside the reactor [2], this can be done by increasing hydrogen recirculation. Another innovative way used in this study is by improving the adsorption capacity and hence the bioavailability of hydrogen. This was done by modifying the immobilized polyfoam matrix and combining micro sorbents in order to increase the total and active surface area of the polymeric matrix and the hydrogen adsorption selectivity. The immobilized matrix was enriched with powdered activated carbon (PAC) to enhance surface area. Additionally, microporous organic polymers (MOPs) were incorporated due to their applications in adsorption, catalysis, gas separation, and storage. Among MOPs, hyper-cross-linked (HCL) resins are particularly effective, featuring a highly porous three-dimensional network with excellent adsorption properties [6]. Structural modifications have been studied to optimize selectivity for specific substances [6]. Examples include X-DV-1-BM (SSA ~1100 m²/g) and X-DV-3GNP-BM, a graphene nanoplatelet-

modified HCL resin with SSA ~ 1600 m²/g and selective adsorption of CO₂ (3.5 wt%) and H₂ (1.5 wt%) [6], [7]. Both HCL MOPs were tested for enhancing the immobilized polymeric matrix. This study aims to develop an efficient anaerobic biological-based biogas upgrading technology by incorporating MOPs and PAC into the polymeric foam immobilization matrix. This approach enhances H₂ and CO₂ adsorption and bioavailability, leading to improved gas transfer rates and biomethanation efficiency in ex-situ upgrading. To our knowledge, this is the first attempt to use micro sorbents to increase surface area and adsorption capacity for H₂ and CO₂ in biological biogas upgrading.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

HCL MOPs (X-DV-1-BM, SSA ~ 1100 m²/g; X-DV-3GNP-BM, SSA ~ 1600 m²/g, selective for CO₂ and H₂ adsorption) were provided by Dr. Rachele Castaldo (NRC, Italy) [6], [7]. PAC Diox Sorb BP2 was obtained from Jacobi Carbons (Sweden). Technical-grade chemicals were from CARLO ERBA Reagents, and hydrophilic polyurethane pre-polymer (Hypol FHP 2002™) was from Dow Chemicals. Anaerobic granular biomass was collected from a UASB reactor (PRIGAT, Israel).

Screening of High-Surface Sorbents (Semi-Batch Tests): Micro sorbents (PAC, MOPs) were tested for biogas upgrading in 0.5 L Tedlar® bags containing grounded UASB biomass, media, and 1% (wet base) MOPs or PAC. A CO₂:H₂ (1:4) gas mix (500 mL) was added to stimulate hydrogenotrophic methanogenesis, with bioreactors incubated at 37°C for 7 cycles. CH₄ fraction, H₂ consumption, and methane production rates were measured.

Composite Polyfoam Preparation: Anaerobic biomass (TS: 100 g/kg, VS: 70 g/kg) was immobilized in HPU foam (AgRobics© method). PAC (16.6 mg/cm³) was incorporated using immersion and Calcium alginate injection methods. XDV1 and XDV3 were injected into the polymeric matrix as immersion was unsuccessful.

Reactor Setup & Operation: Glass anaerobic reactors (440 mL) contained 10 polyfoam cubes (~ 125 cm³). The reactor had liquid and gas inlets, recirculation, and gas outlets, maintaining 25 °C. H₂:CO₂ (4:1) was fed at 1.3 mL/min, with recirculation adjusted over four phases. Biogas was collected in RESTEK® sampling bags, with final CH₄:CO₂:H₂ ratio set at 2:1:4.

Analytical Methods: Biogas composition (CH₄, H₂, CO₂) was analyzed using Agilent 7890B GC with TCD detector. Column temp: 150 °C, injector/detector: 200 °C, sample volume: 250 μ L. COD, TS, and VS were measured per standard wastewater methods.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The Effect of Micro Sorbent Addition on Methane Production in Semi-Batch Experiments

To assess the impact of micro sorbents on biogas upgrading, semi-batch experiments were conducted using a consistent biomass level (sludge) with 1% (wet base) MOPs (XDV1, XDV3) or PAC. A CO₂:H₂ (1:4) gas mix was used to stimulate hydrogenotrophic methanogenesis. Each experiment ran for seven cycles, with reactors emptied and refilled with fresh CO₂ and H₂ after reaching maximum methane content.

Figure 2(a-c) shows methane production for the first three cycles with XDV1, XDV3, and PAC. All sorbents improved %CH₄ production over the sludge control (Blank), with XDV1 exhibiting the highest enhancement. This is attributed to its high adsorption capacity and selectivity for CO₂ and H₂, likely increasing mass transfer into the biofilm, accelerating the bio-methane process, and improving efficiency compared to methane production without adsorbents.

Figure 1. Methane percentage of the first (a), second (b), and third (c) cycles for sludge alone, and sludge with PAC, XDV1, and XDV3 additions.

The Effect of Micro Sorbent Addition on Methane Production in Continuous Experiments

The first continuous experiment examined methane production by hydrogenotrophic methanogens in lab-scale IBBRs, initially by injecting CO₂ and H₂ (1:4 ratio), followed by biogas injection with hydrogen. Four reactors were tested: Blank reactor – immobilized biomass within a polymeric matrix. PAC-impregnated reactor – same polymeric matrix with adsorbed PAC. PAC-alginate reactor – PAC immobilized within the matrix using alginate beads. MOPs-alginate reactor – a combination of XDV1 and XDV3 immobilized with alginate beads.

The 80-day experiment applied varying operational conditions. Figure 2(a) shows that reducing recirculation from 7× to 2× to 0× in the blank reactor decreased %CH₄ from 48% to 43% to 39%, but biogas injection increased %CH₄ from 29% to 55%. The PAC-impregnated reactor had higher %CH₄ than the blank, especially at 7× and 2× recirculation. However, reducing recirculation lowered %CH₄ from 66% to 34%, while biogas injection raised it from 29% to 62%. These findings confirm that biomethanation without gas recirculation is less effective, as recirculation enhances hydrogen mass transfer, improving biogas upgrading via post ex-situ technology [3]. The PAC-alginate reactor consistently produced higher %CH₄ than the blank across all conditions. Notably, without recirculation, %CH₄ was higher than when recirculation was applied. Biogas injection further increased %CH₄ from 29% to 73%, surpassing the first two reactors. The MOPs-alginate reactor achieved the highest %CH₄ across all conditions. While operational conditions had minimal impact, biogas injection increased %CH₄ from 29% to 83%, the highest among all reactors.

Figure 2(b) depicts methane production rates across conditions. In the blank reactor, production remained stable. In the PAC-impregnated reactor, 7× recirculation yielded the highest methane production, but reducing recirculation lowered production, mirroring Figure 2(a).

For the PAC-alginate reactor, 7× recirculation resulted in the lowest methane production rate, similar to the MOPs-alginate reactor, where reducing recirculation led to increased methane production, surpassing the blank. Upon biogas and hydrogen injection into the MOPs-alginate reactor, methane production increased the most, albeit with a high standard deviation. In general, methane production rates declined when biogas was injected, aligning with the drop in hydrogen consumption shown in Figure 2(c). The methane production rate during hydrogenotrophic methanogenesis ranged from 9.7–14.8 mL/h, equivalent to 0.5–0.8 L CH₄/L reactor/day, comparable to reported volumetric CH₄ productivities of 0.65–5.3 L CH₄/L reactor/day in chemoautotrophic CO₂-to-CH₄ conversion experiments [1].

Figure 2(c) shows H₂ consumption across conditions. Before biogas upgrading, H₂ uptake ranged from 73–81% in the blank reactor. The PAC-impregnated reactor showed higher H₂ consumption (84%), though this dropped to 70% when recirculation was removed. The PAC-alginate reactor maintained consistently higher H₂ uptake than both the blank and PAC-impregnated reactors.

The MOPs-alginate reactor had the highest H₂ uptake, with higher consumption at lower

recirculation ratios. However, biogas and hydrogen injection reduced H₂ uptake in all reactors. This is likely due to the high CH₄ content (29% CH₄, 14% CO₂, 57% H₂) in the injected biogas, which lowered the partial pressure and solubility of gases, reducing their bioavailability [8]. Overall, H₂ consumption was highest in the MOPs-alginate reactor, followed by PAC-alginate, PAC-impregnated, and the blank reactor. Figure 2(d) depicts CO₂ consumption, which was generally higher than H₂ uptake, particularly in the blank and PAC-impregnated reactors. Higher CO₂ consumption was observed at 7× recirculation, while PAC-alginate and MOPs-alginate reactors demonstrated high CO₂ uptake, though H₂ consumption was greater.

Figure 2. (a) Percentage of CH₄, (b) Methane production rate, (c) H₂ consumption percentage, and (d) CO₂ percentage in the different IBBRs under varying operational conditions.

CONCLUSIONS

This study demonstrated a novel approach for enhancing biological ex-situ biogas upgrading by incorporating microporous organic polymers (MOPs) and powdered activated carbon (PAC) into an immobilized polyurethane matrix. These modifications improved gas adsorption properties, particularly for hydrogen and carbon dioxide, leading to higher methane content and hydrogen uptake. The MOPs-alginate reactors consistently outperformed PAC-based and control systems, achieving up to 83% CH₄ under biogas injection. These findings confirm the potential of micro sorbents to enhance hydrogenotrophic methanogenesis and reduce reliance on gas recirculation, making the system more energy-efficient and potentially scalable.

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